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**Worldmaking Practices of the Polish Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies:
Geographical Imaginations of the Settlers in the Recovered Territories of Post-1945
Poland**

Abstract

This article focuses on the Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies, an institution established to study Poland's post-1945 "recovered territories". It participated in worldmaking: shaping the geographical imagination and realities of Poland's postwar recovered territories in historically specific ways. Drawing on data from field collaborators, the bureau's archival practices contributed to framing the incorporation of the formerly German regions into Poland. By analyzing these materials, I demonstrate how scientific and political narratives were intertwined with settlers' everyday experiences, revealing how archives became tools of both documentation and active participation in shaping postwar territorial and social realities. While previous research has focused on the methods and processes of resettlement, less attention has been given to the institutions created to plan the process according to scientific criteria. Through a close reading of archival sources, particularly 69 report cards from the bureau's field collaborators in the Szczecin Voivodeship (1947–1948), this study demonstrates that the on-site correspondents, settlers themselves, actively shaped perceptions of the region, constructing narratives designed to guide official policy. In turn, this study offers new insights into how bureaucratic institutions and settlers co-produced knowledge designed to legitimize territorial claims and influenced the realities of postwar Poland's shifting borders.

Keywords: recovered territories; post-1945 Poland; geographical imagination; worldmaking; archiving practices; resettlement

Introduction

After the end of the Second World War, Poland was literally moved westward: it gained regions in the west and north, while losing areas in the East. Whereas the eastern regions were now incorporated into the Soviet Union, Poland, a state transitioning to be entirely ruled by communists, gained industrialized regions in the west, a long coastline along the Baltic Sea, and vast expanses of former Pomeranian and Masurian provinces with their woods, lakes, and huge farms—all at the expense of the defeated German Third Reich. These formerly German lands incorporated into Poland became known as the Recovered Territories¹. Such an operation required specific political activities, including the expulsion of Germans and the management of new settlers who came from the neighboring regions, destroyed cities or were forced to leave the Eastern territories now within the borders of the Soviet Union. The resettlement and expulsion were bolstered by strong efforts of propaganda. The imaginary of recovery and loss

¹ In accordance with the journal's guidelines and to facilitate comprehension for English-speaking readers, I use the spelling recovered territories throughout the text, rather than the convention I follow in Polish, where the term is capitalized and enclosed in quotation marks to signal critical distance from the ideological implications it carries.

in regions subjected to forced migration was used by the Communist government to meet the emotional needs of the settlers². Allegedly, they were here to recover the proto-Polish lands from the hands of hostile Germans,³ collectively blamed for the cruel war that had just ended. Hence, the term “recovered territories:” the acquired lands were presented by official propaganda as “recovered” or “regained” based solely on the fact that some parts of these regions in the past were briefly within the borders of Poland.⁴

From the outset, efforts to regulate who could settle in the recovered territories and how resettlement would occur were shaped by both the settlers’ needs and the political imperatives of the newly reconfigured Polish state. Polish authorities, represented by the Soviet-controlled Polish Committee of National Liberation, prioritized rapid resettlement even before the war ended. It complicated the plans for any kind of scientific resettlement, understood here as the planned, systematic, state-led organization of population movements based on demographic, geographic and ethnographic analyses. The distinction between such a planned resettlement and spontaneous one soon became a key issue, prompting the establishment of the Scientific Council for the Matters of the Recovered Territories in mid-1945 as an advisory body to the Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies, led by statistician Rajmund Buławski. Both institutions approached resettlement through a scientific and statistical lens. Within this context, the bureau created a network of field collaborators, termed correspondents, in 1946, tasked with reporting on settlement conditions on site.

Unlike the prominent scientists associated with the council, these correspondents—settlers themselves—remained anonymous in official reports. However, as I argue, their role was crucial in legitimizing the resettlement process as a structured, knowledge-driven effort, reinforcing the idea of recovery while asserting Polish agency on the ground. In fact, it constituted a certain worldmaking practice, as I argue throughout this article. The recovered territories serve as an ideal laboratory for examining how such a worldmaking unfolded within a specific geographical space. I adhere to the definition of worldmaking as “historically specific ways of practicing the world,”⁵ shaped intentionally by various historical actors, both at the centers and the margins.

Therefore, I put forward the hypothesis that the bureau through its archival practices and the contributions of its field collaborators, actively engaged in worldmaking by shaping the geographical imagination within realities of Poland’s postwar recovered territories. I use the definition of geographical imagination as “the complex of culturally and historically specific geographical knowledge and understanding that characterizes a social group,”⁶ which in turn allows me to explore what were the worldmaking practices of correspondents and the bureau, and how they resulted in specific geographical imagination of a certain region of post-

² Kamila Gieba, 'In Search of the Epic: Settler Narratives from the So-Called Recovered Territories', *Teksty Drugie* 5 (2015) 321–35 (pp. 321–35).

³ Karin Reichenbach, 'The Research Program on the Beginnings of the Polish State between Polish Western Thought and Historical Materialism: Structural Developments and Political Reorientation', *Przegląd Archeologiczny* 65 (2017) 19–34 (pp. 19–34).

⁴ Marta Grzechnik, 'Recovering' Territories: The Use of History in the Integration of the New Polish Western Borderland after World War II, *Europe-Asia Studies* 69 (2017) 668–92 (pp. 668–92); Peter Polak-Springer, *Recovered Territory: A German-Polish Conflict over Land and Culture, 1919-1989* (New York: Berghahn Books, 2015).

⁵ Łukasz Stanek, 'Socialist Worldmaking: The Political Economy of Urban Comparison in the Global Cold War', *Urban Studies* 59 (2022) 1575–1596 (p. 1578). Cf. Tobias Berger, 'Worldmaking from the Margins: Interactions between Domestic and International Ordering in Mid-20th-Century India', *European Journal of International Relations* 28 (2022) 834–58; Sal Clark, 'Contested Worldmaking from 'above' and 'below': Bordered Spaces and Bordered Subjects in Search of Asylum', *Political Geography* 106 (2023) 1–11.

⁶ Denis E. Cosgrove and Veronica Della Dora, 'Mapping Global War: Los Angeles, the Pacific, and Charles Owens's Pictorial Cartography', *Annals of the Association of American Geographers* 95 (2005) 373–390 (p. 388); Derek Gregory, *Geographical Imaginations* (Oxford: Blackwell, 1993).

war Poland, providing the representational frameworks that guided people's perceptions and actions. Essentially, the geographical imagination in question supplied the vision and the narratives regarding the formerly German lands, and those visions were actualized through historical practices in the process of worldmaking.

Furthermore, I claim that anonymization was a deliberate strategy in the use of these materials, which becomes evident in light of the well-documented activities of the bureau and the council, which I will further explore in subsequent sections. These documents were intended to support the scientific nature of the resettlement activities as understood at the time. To make them more objective and usable, they were to be devoid of their users' identities. However, their strength also derived from the fact that they were created by settlers. The anonymization of the carriers of information, juxtaposed with the council's efforts to legitimize their actions, led to a blurring of responsibility amid power struggles and evolving ideas at the core of the resettlement action. The novelty of my approach reveals another dimension of the scientific versus spontaneous character of the resettlement in Poland during the 1940s.

Therefore, I ask: what geographical imaginations were created by the correspondents and by the bureau? Conversely, what were the geographical realities in which these sources were created? To this end, I analysed a specific set of archival materials produced by the bureau, based on field reports from its local collaborators. My focus was on the report cards for the Szczecin Voivodeship—covering the areas of Western and Central Pomerania—from the years 1947–1948. In total, I analyzed 69 cards. In the following sections, I first outline the methods employed to analyze these archival materials. Then, I provide a broader contextual framework for their creation before presenting two case studies that examine geographical imaginations related to the process of recovery with respect to the geographical realities on which they were constructed. The first case explores the experiences of Poles resettled from formerly Polish territories incorporated into the Soviet Union, while the second addresses the self-representation of correspondents as settlers. Through this analysis, I demonstrate that settlers, despite being subjected to political forces that determined the shape of East Central Europe beyond their control, did not merely comply with imposed structures but actively participated in shaping both the geographical imagination and realities of resettlement through the archiving practice.

Methods

When analyzing the collected materials, I follow the methods developed under the so-called ethnographies of encounter.⁷ Therefore, I assumed that in the post-war communities in the recovered territories, there were unequal relations: between correspondents and the bureau, provided by the anonymization of the former and legitimization of the latter with academic authorities; between officials and their clients; and among the various groups of settlers. These assumptions meant that instead of describing the state of these relationships at a specific moment, I focused to their dynamic nature and the variables that affect them. In this regard, the concept expands upon the studies on the dynamics of war-induced migrations, as presented in the seminal works of Piotr Eberhardt, who emphasized that these processes occurred within the context of shifting borders and evolving military and geopolitical influences.⁸ Similarly, Andrzej Gawryszewski pointed out that documentation concerning the

⁷ Lieba Faier and Lisa Rofel, 'Ethnographies of Encounter', *Annual Review of Anthropology* 43 (2014) 363–77.

⁸ Piotr Eberhardt, 'Przemieszczenia ludności na terytorium Polski spowodowane II Wojną Światową', *Dokumentacja Geograficzna* 15 (2000) 1-86 (p. 5).

movement of settlers is scarce and often inadequate until 1950.⁹ Thus, other materials—and methods to interpret them, accordingly—are needed to provide a comprehensive overview of these processes.

When reading the preserved documents of the bureau, I took into account the assumptions of the archival turn present in the contemporary humanities.¹⁰ In other words, I saw archival documents as more than just descriptions of ‘how it was’ or mere representations of various discourses. The stages of working with archives go beyond this layer of criticism, as noted by Michel-Rolph Trouillot.¹¹ Therefore, I clearly delineated the researched material and pay attention to the circumstances of its creation and the goals it served. I started from the materials, using terms adopted by their authors with a critical distance. When creating a narrative, I not only referred to direct quotes, but also indicated the meanings they construct in the described situation. Finally, I strived to show the ambiguity of the histories created by the authors of the sources. For the purposes of this text, I translated the quoted documents into English, which places the reader in a position of necessary trust: they have to rely on the author both as the translator of the sources and as the interpreter of the case studies.

Therefore, the dictionary I used in this article includes words such as the ‘Recovered Territories’ (Polish *Ziemie Odzyskane*), ‘settler’ (*osadnik*) or ‘repatriate’ (*repatriant*). I used these terms because, following the principles of ethnographies of encounter, it is important to understand the purposes behind the specific vocabulary used by a given group and the meanings it carries. At the same time, I am aware that these terms carry ideological elements, and therefore, I maintained a critical distance and carefully distinguished the language of the source from that of scientific description. Here, ethnographic sensitivity supplements the geographical approach, leading me to use these terms with the caveat that my understanding of them results from the meanings embedded in them, not from ideological assumptions.

Hence, the term recovered territories carries a layer of recognition of what is perceived ‘mine’ and ‘belong to me,’ though it is simultaneously tinged with propaganda.¹² The term settler defines anyone who arrived in or remained in the incorporated regions to participate in establishing Polishness in these areas, including through bureaucratic practices. The term repatriate, related to the recovered territories, was meant to signify a return to the =Motherland, as opposed to leaving the homeland that was incorporated into the Soviet Union in 1945.¹³ I consider the language used by the creators of the sources I analyze as a reflection of their attempt to describe their experience. This language was influenced by both the propaganda and discourse generated by the central authorities, as well as by the personal awareness of those who created these sources. A correspondent of the bureau from the vicinity of Chojna perhaps put it most cautiously, writing that ‘the people who came here mostly from the east went through hard times during the war,’ and therefore, the duty of the officials was to

⁹ Andrzej Gawryszewski, 'Zmiany w rozmieszczeniu, ruchu naturalnym, migracjach i strukturze ludności Polski, 1918–2005', *Przegląd Geograficzny* 79 (2007) 461–482 (p. 478).

¹⁰ Terry Cook, 'The Archive(s) Is a Foreign Country: Historians, Archivists, and the Changing Archival Landscape', *The American Archivist* 74 (2011) 600–632; Bernd Frohmann, 'Documentary Ethics, Ontology, and Politics', *Archival Science* 8 (2008) 165–80; Bernd Frohmann, 'Revisiting ‘What Is a Document?’', *Journal of Documentation* 65 (2009) 291–303; Michelle Caswell, 'The Archive’ Is Not an Archives: On Acknowledging the Intellectual Contributions of Archival Studies', *Reconstruction* 16 (2016).

¹¹ Michel-Rolph Trouillot, *Silencing the Past: Power and the Production of History* (Boston: Beacon Press, 1995).

¹² Janusz Jasiński, 'Kwestia Pojęcia Ziemie Odzyskane', in *Ziemie Odzyskane/Ziemie Zachodnie i Północne 1945–2005. 60 lat w granicach państwa polskiego*, ed. by Andrzej Sakson (Poznań: Instytut Zachodni, 2006), pp. 15–26; Zbigniew Mazur, 'O Legitymizowaniu przynależności Ziem Zachodnich i Północnych do Polski', in *Ziemie Odzyskane 1945–2005. Ziemie Zachodnie i Północne. 60 Lat w Granicach Państwa Polskiego*, ed. by Andrzej Sakson (Poznań: Instytut Zachodni, 2006), pp. 27–44.

¹³ Grzechnik, 'Recovering’ Territories'.

understand not only the repatriates' material needs but also their mental state.¹⁴ 'Wanting to mentally tune the population to love and trust in the Offices and the State' he continued, 'we must treat the citizens with favor and courtesy, even if it is sometimes hard for us.'¹⁵ As this quote implies, the geographical imagination and realities went hand in hand when it comes to the postwar situation in the recovered territories.

Archival Materials

The bureau had correspondents throughout the recovered territories, recruited from various groups of settlers and instructed to provide their assessments of events occurring on-site. The pieces of information sent by the correspondents were preserved as part of the archives of the Ministry of the Recovered Territories. Subsequently, they have been kept in the Archive of Modern Records in Warsaw, Poland. The original reports by the correspondents were not preserved. Instead, what was archived, is a selection, partly analyzed and prepared by the bureau's employees as 'a partial copy of the comments received from correspondents,' sent on July 14, 1947, to the Ministry of the Recovered Territories and later supplemented. Employees of the bureau sent them with the thought that 'they would be of interest to the local Office [the Ministry].'¹⁶ This already signals the archiving practices of the institutions in question, gathering information for further use, organizing and preserving its own records and documents in the belief they could be useful in the future. In the case mentioned, the bureau's employees partially analyzed and prepared the correspondents' reports, indicating their role in curating and preserving these records as part of their archiving efforts. However, with the liquidation of the Ministry, these efforts proved futile. Liquidated in January 1949, the Ministry's assets were redistributed, and its role was transferred, among others, to the Ministry of Public Administration, which initially managed issues related to the incorporated lands.¹⁷ The archiving efforts at both levels—first by the correspondents and then by the bureau—were ultimately unsuccessful. However, the preserved archives still reflect the endeavor and the belief that they could be useful, as well as the active involvement of the settlers themselves in the resettlement process. As such, they reflect not only the geographical imagination of the recovered territories, but also worldmaking practices.

Sending these cards to the Ministry was meant to play a crucial role. The bureau aimed at transforming scattered, localized experiences of the correspondents into a structured, authoritative narrative of the recovered territories. As settlers documented their observations, challenges, and assessments of the resettlement process, their reports were aggregated and synthesized by the bureau, shaping a standardized representation of the region. As a result, they were meant to contribute to the geographical imagination of the recovered territories as a new part of Poland, where process of resettlement occurred with at least some attempt to make it according to a plan.

These clippings: excerpts or selected portions of original documents that have been copied from larger texts, look as follows. In the left upper corner, an internal number is typewritten and underlined, though the reference material is not specified. In the right upper corner, the month, year, and type of locality are written. Since the correspondents were not recruited from cities, all analyzed materials are labeled either 'village 1' or '2' (*wieś-1*, *wieś-*

¹⁴ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

¹⁵ Anonymous, October 1947, MZO AMR, folio 299.

¹⁶ Biuro Studiów Osadniczo-Przesiedleńczych [the Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies] to Departament Osiedleńczy [Department of Resettlement] at the Ministry of the Recovered Territories, 14 July 1947, MZO AMR, folio 1.

¹⁷ Strauchold, 'Okoliczności Likwidacji Ministerstwa Ziemi Odzyskanych'.

2), suggesting that in some counties, correspondents were from at least two different localities. Below this, the voivodeship (*województwo*) and county (*powiat*) are indicated (Fig. 1). For the purposes of this article, I analyzed all 69 cards for Szczecin voivodeship (Fig. 2), from the years 1947-1948. This particular voivodeship existed since 1946 until 1950.

Figure 1 One of the cards showing how they are preserved. Archive of Modern Records in Warsaw, Ministerstwo Ziem Odzyskanych [Ministry of the Recovered Territories], sig. 1662, Uwagi i informacje korespondentów terenowych o stosunkach na Ziemiach Odzyskanych [Remarks and information by the field correspondents about the relationships in the Recovered Territories, f. 123.

These cards not only provided insights into the reality of the recovered territories but also reflected the perceptions of particular settlers who wished to share their views with the scientific authorities. Simultaneously, they were used by the bureau to shape the representation of the formerly German lands, contributing to the production of maps. These maps, in turn, were intended to illustrate a range of problems encountered in a given county, from the level of danger in an area to the specific illnesses that were more likely to be contracted there compared to other counties. To some extent, this information also helped consolidate a unified geographical imagination of these lands, at least for the period the Ministry existed. Additionally, the sole act of typing and sending these reports to the Ministry, the central institution, demonstrated an attempt to influence the geographical imagination of these regions. As such, these archival documents played a key role in constructing a representation of the place, showing the settler's attitudes and shaping the broader plans for the scientific resettlement process. In this way, the documents were instrumental in consolidating the authority of the bureau, which sent them to the Ministry as tools for legitimizing resettlement actions and maintaining a sense of order and accountability within the institution overseeing the scientific resettlement.

Figure 2 Map showing the regions incorporated into Poland as 'Recovered Territories' (light green), with Western and Central Pomerania (in red) within the borders of the former provinces of Pommern and Grenzmark Posen-Westpreußen.¹⁸ Source: Wikipedia Commons with modifications by the author of the article, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported license.

When it comes to which cards were typewritten and sent, there was no correlation between the number of inhabitants in 1946 of a given county¹⁹ and the quantity of cards sent (Fig. 3). For example, in this collection, the largest county, Słupsk, is not represented at all, while the relatively less populated county of Gryfice—ranked ninth in terms of the number of inhabitants—is represented by nine cards compared to eight cards from Białogard county, which is ranked third. Additionally, there was no correlation between the area of a county and the number of cards; for instance, the relatively small Gryfice county, which had the highest number of cards at nine, ranked only 21st in terms of size. There were no cards from seven counties: Słupsk, Sławno, Stargard, Miastko, Drawsko, Szczecin (city), and Wolin. Considering the strategy of recruiting correspondents, it is understandable why Szczecin (city) was excluded—as the correspondents were not recruited from cities—the absence of other counties seems to lack clear rationale and appears to have been contingent solely on the discretion of officials who selected which information should be turned into clippings and subsequently sent to the Ministry (Fig. 3). Thus, it also points to self-archiving practices of the

¹⁸ For the detailed map showing the migration to and from Poland between 1945 and 1959 please see, Karolina Ćwiek-Rogalska, *Ziemie. Historie odzyskiwania i utraty* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Radia Naukowego, 2024).

¹⁹ *Powszechny sumaryczny spis ludności z dn. 14 II 1946 r.*, ed. by Kazimierz Romaniuk et al. (Warszawa: Główny Urząd Statystyczny, 1947), pp. 13–14.

officials.

Figure 3 The counties are ranked according to the number of inhabitants in 1946, and the bars illustrate the number of cards preserved from a given county.

The close reading of the preserved materials allows me to address a frequent problem associated with the archival turn, “a loose configuration of writing, theory, art, and visual culture that uses the terminology or image of the archive to describe a set of ideas about the structural power of history and its ideological and technological conditions.”²⁰ In what follows, I do not claim to propose a new take on theorized archives nor critique the over-use of archival-specific language. Instead, I provide ample historical context to make sense of the material, to see how the archival materials in question were produced, and to embed them in the historical and geographical milieu in which they were created. At the same time, I treat the archival materials as “epistemic things,”²¹ which in turn allows me to better understand their significance for the institutions in question, the techniques these institutions used, and their role in creating the “recovery” as the basis for postwar Polish policy, regardless of the political views of the persons involved.

It seems, however, that the correspondents themselves were not of intense interest to the bureau. Hence, the materials provided by the bureau to the Ministry warrant more detailed questions about the correspondents, especially in light of the archival materials they created. Thus, my follow-up questions concerning the geographical imaginations created by the bureau, in the context of the concept of recovery versus the geographical realities onsite, will focus on two specific case studies. These are: how did the correspondents depict one specific group of postwar settlers, Poles displaced from the formerly Polish territories annexed by the Soviet Union; and how did correspondents create their own self-image given their anonymized status imposed by the bureau’s methodology?

Scientific Resettlement: Origins and Structure

From the very beginning, attempts were made to regulate who could move to the recovered territories and how this movement would occur. Such plans and regulations resulted from the understandable needs of settlers, as well as the needs of the emerging state—Poland within new borders, in a new bloc of political affiliation, with its identity, geographic, and political vector shifted in a different direction. It is difficult to determine the exact start date of the resettlement of the German territories that were incorporated into Poland in 1945. Following the initial decision made at the Tehran Conference in 1943 to shift Poland westward and the more concrete proposals put forth by the USSR at the Yalta Conference in February 1945,²² a final treaty was anticipated but never realized. The Potsdam Agreement, regarded as provisional by various historical actors, later including the future CDU-led West German government and strengthened by the Soviet leaders such as Nikita Khrushchev, further complicates this timeline.²³ Nevertheless, the strategy of the Polish authorities, at the time

²⁰ Sara Callahan, 'When the Dust Has Settled: What Was the Archival Turn, and Is It Still Turning?', *Art Journal* 83 (2024) 74-88 (p. 74).

²¹ Hans-Jörg Rheinberger, *Toward a History of Epistemic Things: Synthesizing Proteins in the Test Tube* (Stanford: University of Stanford Press, 1997); Jason Lustig, 'Epistemologies of the Archive: Toward a Critique of Archival Reason', *Archival Science* 20 (2020) 65–89.

²² Gerard Labuda, *Polska granica zachodnia: Tysiąc lat dziejów politycznych* (Poznań: Wydawnictwo Poznańskie, 1974).

²³ Jan Musekamp, *Zwischen Stettin und Szczecin: Metamorphosen einer Stadt von 1945 bis 2005* (Leipzig: Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2010), p. 128.

represented in the country by the Soviet-controlled Polish Committee of National Liberation, was to resettle the lands in question as soon as possible. Consequently, some of the former forced laborers, as well as prisoners of war present in these regions that were to be incorporated to Poland, became the first settlers.²⁴ Additionally, numerous transports of people displaced from the formerly Polish Eastern Borderlands were relocated in early spring of 1945, before the war officially ended.²⁵

Many settlers, encouraged by propaganda to seek better living conditions in the recovered territories, included people from the war-ravaged interior seeking upward mobility or escape from the new order, like Home Army soldiers and partisans. Almost three million people migrated from Central Poland to the recovered territories due to hunger for land. Various groups of settlers are extensively described in scholarship, either by their places of origin or by where they settled. These groups include people displaced from the East,²⁶ re-emigrants from the West,²⁷ partially resettlers from the Elder Lands—regions that were Polish pre-1939 and remained within postwar Poland, often simplified to Central Poland, Polish interior, as well as autochthons, the natives,²⁸ and those forcibly resettled during Operation Wisła. This 1947 event, executed by the Polish communist authorities, involved the compulsory relocation of approximately 140,000 Ukrainians, Boykos, and Lemkos from southeastern regions of postwar Poland to the recovered territories.²⁹

The distinction between planned and spontaneous settlement was recognized as a problem relatively early. In the summer of 1945, it was one of the main issues reported by the newly established Scientific Council for the Matters of the Recovered Territories (*Rada Naukowa dla Zagadnień Ziem Odzyskanych*). The council, founded in Kraków by the Minister of Public Administration and the Plenipotentiary, Władysław Kiernik—since a separate Ministry for the Recovered Territories was not established until November of that year³⁰—held its first meeting over three days, from July 30 to August 1, 1945. At the time, the Potsdam Conference and resettlement actions in the territories discussed at Cecilienhof Palace were still ongoing.

The council functioned as an advisory body to the Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies, led by Rajmund Buławski until his death in 1947. Buławski, a statistician responsible for the Polish national census of 1931, significantly influenced the bureau and the council's work with his research interests. Both quantitative methods and general statistical observations were central to the aims and activities of these bodies. Consequently, they already presented a certain geographical imagination. As a culturally specific concept, it underscores the processes of transmission and interaction, as well as the role of representations in structuring the perceptions and experiences of the historical actors in question. Simultaneously, it illustrates that the recovered territories were understood as a certain geographical entity,

²⁴ Krystyna Kersten and Tomasz Szarota, 'Kształtowanie się pierwszego planu osadnictwa Ziem Zachodnich w 1945 r. (wybór dokumentów)', *Polska Ludowa: Materiały i Studia* 5 (1966) 28–189.

²⁵ Grzegorz Hryciuk, *Przesiedleńcy: Wielka Epopeja Polaków, 1944-1946* (Kraków: Wydawnictwo Literackie, 2023).

²⁶ Hryciuk, *Przesiedleńcy*

²⁷ Aneta Nisiobęcka, 'Reemigracja Polaków z Francji oraz ich adaptacja w Polsce Ludowej w latach 1945–1950', *Dzieje Najnowsze* 48 (2016) 169–78.

²⁸ Andrzej Sakson, *Mazurzy, Społeczność Pogranicza* (Poznań: Instytut Zachodni, 1990).

²⁹ Grzegorz Motyka, *Akcja "Wisła" '47: komunistyczna czystka etniczna* (Kraków: Wydawnictwo Literackie, 2023).

³⁰ Grzegorz Strauchold, 'Okoliczności Likwidacji Ministerstwa Ziem Odzyskanych', *Komunikaty Mazursko-Warmińskie* 1 (2015) 111–20; Mieczysław Jaworski, *Na piastowskim szlaku: Działalność Ministerstwa Ziem Odzyskanych w latach 1945-1948* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Ministerstwa Obrony Narodowej, 1973); Karolina Ćwiek-Rogalska and Izabela Mrzygłód, 'Futuryści z MZO. Organizowanie się Ministerstwa Ziem Odzyskanych w czasie i przestrzeni', *Acta Baltico-Slavica* 46 (2022) 1-26.

embedded within some expectations stemming not only from propaganda, but also scientific activities of institutions such as the council.

The predominance of settlers, both actual and potential, and the near absence of German inhabitants to be expelled, allowed the involved scientists to plan the resettlement not only before the final decisions of the Allies but also to treat the formerly German territories as empty laboratories where the resettlement actions could be undertaken. Therefore, the resettlement action was presented as not without challenges, yet it deliberately overlooked the most obvious one, namely that the German inhabitants were still present. Instead, it emphasized the toil and effort of Polish society as a settler community, and in this sense, also the undertakings by the scientists.

This led to an unexpected outcome in the creation of an auxiliary tool by the bureau: a network of field correspondents (*korespondenci*), established in mid-1946 and continued until 1948. The term “correspondent” was used here in a dual sense. Firstly, it was similar to the contemporary term “reporter,” referring to a person employed by a particular institution and responsible for reporting on specific subjects or providing correspondence from abroad. Secondly, it referred to someone who writes letters, as the correspondents were tasked with sending their observations to the bureau by mail. Since the meaning of the word is similar in both Polish and English, I have chosen to use the term “correspondent” as an appropriate equivalent for the purposes of this text.

The network of correspondents, anonymized in the materials provided by the bureau to other institutions, stood in sharp contrast to the well-known names of the scientists involved in the council, who were meant to legitimize the advisory character of the bureau. However, as a thesis I put forward, it was precisely the involvement of the correspondents—who were themselves settlers—that was intended to enhance the scientific aspect of the resettlement and emphasize Polish agency on site. It was to further strengthen the geographical imagination of the “recovery” of the formerly German lands, pursued by the council and the bureau.

To understand why the scientific approach to resettlement could have been initiated so swiftly in a war-ravaged country, it is essential to recognize that, firstly, the notion of viewing the contemporary Western Polish regions as inherently Slavic was already popular during the interwar period. This idea was further popularized by the 1930s non-fiction work by Józef Kisielewski “Ziemia gromadzi prochy” [The Earth Gathers Ashes].³¹ Secondly, during the war, the circles connected to historian Zygmunt Wojciechowski, who later became the director of the Institute of Western Affairs and was influential among right-wing thinkers in the interwar period,³² continued their work. The idea that the victory over the Third Reich must result in shifting Polish borders westward became seen as obvious and widely accepted,³³ for instance, among those working with the underground organization “Ojczyzna” [Fatherland].³⁴ This groundwork enabled a swift transition to formalization, allowing the bureau and the council to commence its work early in a relatively undamaged Kraków.³⁵

Hence, the foundations for the idea of resettlement—encompassing both the spontaneous right to settle German lands and the scientific vision of colonization—originated

³¹ Jakub Telec, 'Piotr Zaremba i generacja 1910', *Autobiografia Literatura Kultura Media* 3 (2014) 165–76; Kazimierz Kozłowski, 'Kilka uwag o specyfice patriotyzmu lokalnego. O dwóch mitach założycielskich polskiego Szczecina', *Acta Cassubiana* 17 (2015) 199–212.

³² Zbigniew Mazur, *Antenaci: O politycznym rodowodzie Instytutu Zachodniego* (Poznań: Instytut Zachodni, 2002); Markus Krzoska, *Für ein Polen an Oder und Ostsee: Zygmunt Wojciechowski (1900–1955) als Historiker und Publizist* (Osnabrück: Fibre, 2003).

³³ Maciej Górny, 'Po Co Nam Ten Mit? Ziemia Odzyskane', *Przegląd Polityczny* 65 (2004) (p. 122).

³⁴ Grzechnik, 'Recovering Territories', pp. 669–70.

³⁵ Danielle Drozdowski, 'Using History in the Streetscape to Affirm Geopolitics of Memory', *Political Geography* 42 (2014) 66–78.

from the so-called Western thought, an interwar intellectual movement in which the Piast myth played a major role.³⁶ The House of Piast was the first historical ruling dynasty of Poland, beginning with the first documented Polish monarch, Duke Mieszko I, in the tenth-century. In the discourse on the recovered territories, the Piasts were associated with what was seen as the traditional development of Polish statehood towards the northwest, in which the Baltic Sea played an important role and the Oder River was considered the natural border of the Polish state.³⁷ Furthermore, this narrative incorporated an inevitable hostility towards the Germans, which later propaganda quickly seized upon, creating the image of an eternal German, amalgamated from various historical figures, such as a Teutonic knight, a supporter of Kulturkampf in the nineteenth century, or a Nazi.³⁸

In terms of organization, the resettlement process was a combination of planned and spontaneous actions, forcing Polish authorities to impose order on the prevailing chaos. From an administrative perspective, an institution dedicated to manage the flow of settlers was established in 1944: the State Repatriation Office.³⁹ To oversee the administration of the newly acquired territories, the General Plenipotentiary for the Recovered Territories was instituted. At the same time, this authority represented the escalating tensions within the emerging state government, which comprised both communist (PPR, *Polska Partia Robotnicza*, Polish Workers' Party) and agrarian (PSL, *Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe*, Polish People's Party) representatives. Initially, the General Plenipotentiary was the communist Edward Ochab, succeeded later by the agrarian Władysław Kiernik.⁴⁰

Formally, the Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies was established in July 1945 by the Minister of Public Administration. In principle, it was intended to be a scientific and research body tasked with collecting data 'needed to carry out the settlement action.'⁴¹ It also had the authority to initiate action projects, including legislation. It operated as an independent unit, with a separate Director and a scientific and administrative division. The somewhat official status of the bureau was reinforced by the fact that its employees received remuneration equivalent to that of officials in the Ministry of Public Administration.

Notably, the first session of the council—apart from the customary speeches by the minister—was inaugurated with two papers presented by Stanisław Pietkiewicz⁴² and Antoni Wrzosek, both geographers, along with Buławski himself. Wrzosek addressed the issue of the potential administrative division of the incorporated lands, while Pietkiewicz presented a regional resettlement plan. These presentations were further supplemented by Buławski's

³⁶ Grzechnik, 'Recovering' Territories'.

³⁷ Gerard Labuda, *Ziemie Zachodnie w granicach Macierzy: Drogi integracji* (Poznań: Wydawnictwo Poznańskie, 1966).

³⁸ Edmund Dmitrów, *Niemcy i okupacja hitlerowska w oczach Polaków: Poglądy i opinie z lat 1945-1948* (Warszawa: Czytelnik, 1987); Hans Henning Hahn and Robert Traba, *Polsko-niemieckie miejsca pamięci* (volumes I–IV, Scholar: Warszawa, 2013–2015); Igor Kąkolewski, 'Przekłęci i Bohaterowie', in *Wyobrażenia Przeszłości. Polsko-Niemieckie Miejsca Pamięci*, ed. by Robert Traba and Hans Henning Hahn (Scholar: Warszawa, 2015), 73–96; Izabela Surynt, 'Krzyżak', in *Interakcje. Leksykon Komunikowania Polsko-Niemieckiego*, ed. by Alfred Gall et al. (Moguncja, Wrocław, Praga, 2014), <http://www.polska-niemcy-interakcje.pl/articles/show/58>.

³⁹ Stefan Banasiak, *Działalność osadnicza Państwowego Urzędu Repatriacyjnego na Ziemiach Odzyskanych w latach 1945-1947* (Poznań: Instytut Zachodni, 1963).

⁴⁰ Paweł Kacprzak, 'Polityka władz polskich wobec ludności niemieckiej w okresie funkcjonowania Ministerstwa Ziem Odzyskanych', *Acta Universitatis Wratislaviensis. Przegląd Prawa i Administracji* 78 (2008) 31–51; Tomasz Tadeusz Majer, 'Kształtowanie się modelu zarządu Ziem Odzyskanych w latach 1944-1945', *Studia Prawnoustrojowe* 42 (2018) 389–402.

⁴¹ Minister Administracji Publicznej [the Minister for Public Administration], Internal decree no. 7, July 19, 1945, MZO AMR, folio 1.

⁴² Elżbieta Biłska-Wodecka et al., 'Polish Geography and Polish Geographers under Nazi Occupation', *Journal of Historical Geography* 75 (2022) 1–13.

comments on the status of Polish Germans, addressing the questions of expulsion and the exceptions for those who were to remain in postwar Poland.⁴³

The notes from the subsequent sessions, as well as the related papers, were subsequently published. In the first volume, the initial presentation of the council and the issues of resettlement were outlined.⁴⁴ This was followed by volume two, where Buławski addressed the challenges of resettlement in villages, organized farms, and towns.⁴⁵ Volume three included papers on the organization of resettlement by geographers Pietkiewicz and Orlicz, along with Wrzosek, complemented by a piece by ethnographer Kazimierz Dobrowolski on the resettlers and introduced by an article by Władysław Skowron on the demography of postwar migrations.⁴⁶ In all these papers, the issue of Germans and their expulsion was only marginally addressed.

Although the bureau conducted its own research, the idea of creating the council was to strengthen it and make it more legitimate in the eyes of public opinion. The council consisted of 108 members, mostly professors from various Polish universities, with diverse disciplinary backgrounds related to settlement issues.⁴⁷ As the bureau was based in Kraków, it aroused some controversy and simultaneously proved that the council was of interest to the broader public. Although the introduction to the first volume of the council proceedings, published in 1946 (a bit later than the subsequent volumes), claimed that ‘the broader public was regularly informed about the council’s work through the press,’⁴⁸ it was precisely the location of the bureau headquarters that intrigued the public. An article in ‘Trybuna Robotnicza’ [The Workers’ Tribune], one of the largest dailies of postwar Poland, published a text in July 1946 entitled “Kraków cannot be the seat of the Scientific Council of the Recovered Territories.”⁴⁹ It suggested that the headquarters should be in Wrocław (formerly German Breslau), the largest city of the recovered territories. Rajmund Buławski, the then Director of the Bureau, replied that ‘regardless of whether it will be Kraków or Wrocław, ... the decisive authority here is the Ministry of the Recovered Territories, while the council is only an advisory body.’⁵⁰ This would mean that the attempt to improve the flow of information between the local and central levels was deferred, which the decision-makers were aware of. It could also mean that the ‘scientific’ aspect of the settlement action, which was carefully brought to the foreground, was clearly fictitious to all those involved. This view could be strengthened by the declaration published in the aforementioned volume in 1946, claiming that ‘many of the council’s recommendations have already been reflected in the Government’s implementation actions’ and especially that ‘many issues have been resolved or alleviated in the meantime.’⁵¹ The issues were only provisionally specified further.

Thus, the purpose of creating a network of on-site correspondents was to maintain the impression that planned settlement actions, based on theoretical models, were still possible. It was assumed that the settlement would proceed in accordance with geographical zones

⁴³ *I Sesja Rady Naukowej dla Zagadnień Ziem Odzyskanych, 30 VII - 1 VIII 1945 r. Sprawozdanie ogólne*, ed. by Rajmund Buławski, vol. I (Kraków, 1946), p. 2.

⁴⁴ *I Sesja Rady Naukowej*, p. 2.

⁴⁵ *I Sesja Rady Naukowej dla Zagadnień Ziem Odzyskanych, 30 VII-1 VIII 1945 r., z. II, Problemy osadniczo-przesiedleńcze Ziem Odzyskanych*, ed. by Rajmund Buławski, vol. II (Kraków, 1945).

⁴⁶ Władysław Skowron et al., *I Sesja Rady Naukowej Dla Zagadnień Ziem Odzyskanych, 30 VII-1 VIII 1945 r., z. III. Zagadnienia ogólne osadnictwa Ziem Odzyskanych* (Kraków, 1945).

⁴⁷ A full list of the members was included in Rajmund Buławski, *I Sesja Rady Naukowej Dla Zagadnień Ziem Odzyskanych, 30 VII - 1 VIII 1945 r. Sprawozdanie Ogólne*, volume I (Kraków: 1946) 8–10.

⁴⁸ *I Sesja Rady Naukowej*, pp. 8-10.

⁴⁹ N.a., Kraków nie może być siedzibą Rady Naukowej Ziem Odzyskanych, *Trybuna Robotnicza* 193, 16 July 1956, p. 3.

⁵⁰ Letter from Rajmund Buławski to Władysław Gomułka, July 17, 1946, MZO AMR, folios 181-182.

⁵¹ Buławski, *I Sesja Rady Naukowej*, vol. 1, p. 5.

separated along the parallels, divided into regions with similar climates and natural conditions.⁵² As a result, such a homogeneous settlement would guarantee that a new but homogeneous Polish community would emerge. By 1947, however, the bureau realized that such a plan was no longer feasible, admitting that the spontaneous settlement often prevailed. Regardless of whether the bureau was aware that some of its projects were fictitious, or whether its employees still believed it was possible to control the settlement and resettlement actions at least partially, it did not give up gathering the data. The correspondents' reports are the basis of my analysis for more than one reason: the role of correspondents, their relations with the bureau, especially the process of anonymization, and the reflections on themselves and others present in the preserved archival material, provide valuable knowledge about how the bureaucracy created Polishness in formerly German territories in the first postwar years.

Correspondents of the Bureau

The bureau had correspondents throughout the recovered territories, but their range was not well-defined. The recovered territories encompassed a highly heterogeneous area, including Western and Central Pomerania in the West and Northwest, Lubusz Land in the West, Lower Silesia in the Southwest, parts of Silesia in the South, and Eastern Pomerania, Warmia, and Masuria in the North and Northeast. These lands differed not only in geographical location but also in the character of prewar German cultures⁵³ and postwar settlement conditions. The term 'Recovered Territories' obscured this heterogeneity to create a unifying vision.⁵⁴ As such, it served also other purposes in the bureau's everyday research practice: by understanding postwar Polish geography in this way, the data sent by correspondents were comparable from the beginning, requiring no further explanation for their use. The correspondents were recruited from various groups, including employees of the PUR (State Repatriation Office), general administration, and local self-government. This category comprised one-third of all correspondents, totaling 100 out of 300 individuals.

The bureau limited the extent to which correspondents could provide free impressions, requiring responses to follow a fixed pattern. Although the specific instructions have not been preserved in the archive, it is known that correspondents were provided with questionnaires addressing the development of relations in the recovered territories. According to the Bureau's assurances, correspondents were 'not to be constrained in expressing their opinion,' as the instructions included guidelines on 'correct methods of observation and the manner of presenting certain opinions, such as grading in grades.' However, these grading assessments are absent from the existing documentation. The correspondents did not receive payment for their work; it was treated as 'voluntary civic service.'⁵⁵ Occasionally, they received some of the bureau's publications and were reimbursed for postage and paper, which was significant given the high value of paper at the time.

At that time, specifically in mid-1946, the establishment of a network of on-site correspondents was justified as an innovative solution. The bureau believed that the data provided by these correspondents would 'enrich or supplement the normal sources of knowledge of existing relations.' This seemingly minor reference indicates that even from Kraków, far removed from the recovered territories, a clear discrepancy was visible between

⁵² Małgorzata Praczyk, *Pamięć środowiskowa we wspomnieniach osadników na „Ziemiach Odzyskanych”* (Poznań: Instytut Historii UAM, 2018).

⁵³ Andreas Kossert, *Kalte Heimat: Die Geschichte der Deutschen Vertriebenen nach 1945* (München: Siedler Verlag, 2008).

⁵⁴ *Region czy regiony? Ziemie Zachodnie i Północne 1945-1989*, ed. by Wojciech Kucharski et al. (Wrocław: Ośrodek Pamięć i Przyszłość, 2022).

⁵⁵ Zamierzenia Biura Studiów Osadniczo-Przesiedleńczych na rok 1948, n.d., MZO AMR, folio 86.

the official, central discourse, often generalized and quantitative, referred to here as ‘normal sources of knowledge,’ and local issues revealed through qualitative data. The hesitation in the information received is evident in the assurance that the ‘bureau systematically uses the information received, processing it using a strictly objective method.’ Although there were complaints about the imprecision of the data provided, the initiative of the correspondents was praised for ‘providing new insights into various problems in the field of social or economic policy, important for normalizing relations in the recovered territories.’⁵⁶ Consequently, the assumed scope of information was rather limited.

Geographical imagination I: the Repatriates from the East

It is estimated that between 1944 and 1949, approximately 1,507,000 people were officially repatriated,⁵⁷ with an additional 500,000 relocating beyond formal channels. Consequently, a total of 2,207,716 people from the territories annexed by the Soviet Union migrated to the newly defined borders of Poland.⁵⁸ The majority of these individuals used to live in contemporary Ukraine, followed by Belarus, other former Soviet republics, and Lithuania.⁵⁹ This heterogeneous and sizable group was predominantly resettled through official means. However, it was not the largest group of settlers, as this distinction belonged to those from the Elder Lands, even when considering the subsequent repatriations from the USSR of the 1950s. The term ‘repatriation’ does not accurately capture the reality of the situation, as these individuals were displaced or expatriated from their homes. Nonetheless, as Eberhardt notes, the term was widely used, and introducing a new term could cause ‘terminological confusion.’⁶⁰ Despite this, there are attempts to elucidate the reasons for its usage and the context in which it should be understood.⁶¹ Considering the scale and methods by which the group was resettled, they represented a significant topic in reports sent by correspondents. Thus, I will follow the matters connected to the repatriates as they exemplify the means of how worldmaking practices centered on them enhanced the construction of a specific geographical imagination during the settlement of formerly German lands.

In the first place, attention was given to the interactions between different groups of settlers and the repatriates. The conflict between repatriates and resettlers coming from Central Poland was particularly pronounced. The same issue was extensively addressed in the fieldwork conducted by Stanisław Nowakowski three years later, in 1949, in Opole Silesia.⁶² In the field reports of the correspondents, a certain geographical imagination of the repatriates was conveyed. The correspondents primarily mentioned tensions between officials from the Polish interior and their clients, who were repatriated from the East. A correspondent from Pырzyce noted that ‘today it would be appropriate to start educating resettlers and explain to them, starting from the highest authorities of the county together with officials, that an eastern repatriate is the same Pole as them and maybe even better than them.’⁶³ The correspondent suggested that the repatriates could be considered better because, according to him, resettlers

⁵⁶ Zamierzenia, MZO AMR, folios 86-88.

⁵⁷ Kazimierz Piesowicz, 'Wielkie ruchy migracyjne w latach 1945-1950. Część I', *Studia Demograficzne* 4 96 (1988), (p. 55).

⁵⁸ Eberhardt, 'Przemieszczenia ludności na terytorium Polski spowodowane II Wojną Światową', p. 52.

⁵⁹ Eberhardt, 'Przemieszczenia ludności na terytorium Polski spowodowane II Wojną Światową', p. 52.

⁶⁰ Eberhardt, 'Przemieszczenia ludności na terytorium Polski spowodowane II Wojną Światową', p. 49.

⁶¹ Wojciech Marciniak, 'Uwagi o kontekstach znaczeniowych pojęcia „repatriacja” z ZSRR oraz o nabywaniu z jej tytułu obywatelstwa polskiego', *Studia z Historii Społeczno-Gospodarczej XIX i XX wieku* 18 (2017) 79–93.

⁶² Stefan Nowakowski, *Adaptacja ludności na Śląsku Opolskim* (Poznań: Instytut Zachodni, 1957).

⁶³ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

came to the recovered territories ‘in pursuit of the golden fleece.’⁶⁴

By using this phrase, he avoided directly accusing them of what Eugeniusz Paukszta, a Polish writer, whose work prominently features the recovered territories, did not hesitate to state. In the same year, Paukszta wrote in the periodical “Polska Zachodnia” [Western Poland] that resettlers were ‘mockers,’ ‘people with no backbone,’ ‘with a haughty face,’ ‘solidly situated in luxury apartments,’ and holding ‘lucrative jobs.’⁶⁵ Conversely, the repatriates, as described by the correspondent from Pyrzyce, ‘came following the voice of blood and heart, abandoning their ancestors’ nests ... heading towards an uncertain future.’⁶⁶ The correspondent did not clearly define the reasons for this abandonment. The Eastern Borderlands and the causes for their loss were officially unspoken. However, in constructing the model of an ideal settler, the principle of sincerity of beliefs and disregard for self-interest became prominent. Maria Tomczak, in her work on the image of a settler in the Polish press, wrote that while autochthons, re-emigrants, and resettlers were met with distrust, repatriates were viewed as a ready-made model of the new ‘man of the West,’ inhabiting the ‘recovered’ Western and Northern Territories.⁶⁷ This image of the repatriate was, however, more complex. It was shaped by both top-down propaganda narratives and firsthand accounts of how repatriates were treated. This duality bore the hallmarks of the Kresy, the Polish Eastern Borderlands, from the interwar period. The reports of correspondents, as they were later sent to the Ministry, reinforced this ambiguous image. In emphasizing the need for special cultural and hygienic care for repatriates, the correspondent from Pyrzyce echoed the Second Polish Republic’s civilizing mission towards the Borderlands.⁶⁸ This mission, in the collective imagination, ambiguously placed the Kresy as both a thoroughly Polish region and a synonym for backwardness. Connecting the “repatriation” and the “recovery” was a meaning-making practice: the repatriates were believed to be model settlers, at the same time some institutional effort was required to make them so.

Maria Tomczak also emphasized that the mutual reluctance between resettlers and repatriates stemmed from the former’s belief that the formerly German lands were owed to them as compensation for the six-year German occupation, and that the newcomers from the East sought to take this reward away from them. However, in the remarks of the correspondent from Pyrzyce—as well as in the article by Paukszta—another perspective emerges: the belief that the resettlers, being geographically closer, found it easier to move to the recovered territories. As a result, they relocated faster and were the first to occupy the places, while repatriates arrived later due to the longer distance they had to travel.

However, the matter was not so unambiguous, as the local bureaucracy, predominantly composed of resettlers from Central Poland, often determined the right of ownership not by priority of arrival but by affiliation with a particular group of settlers. The correspondent from Pyrzyce noted that ‘the most painful are the quite frequent instances of taking away the house occupied by the repatriate and handing it over to the resettler, because he is an official of the county or has better connections with the officials of the county, and their intervention should be supported.’⁶⁹ Thus, he characterizes the repatriates as subjects of

⁶⁴ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁶⁵ Eugeniusz Paukszta, ‘Rachunek Kulturalny’, *Polska Zachodnia. Ilustrowany tygodnik dla wszystkich*, 1947, p. 2.

⁶⁶ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁶⁷ Maria Tomczak, ‘Obraz osadników w prasie i publicystyce polskiej’, in *Ziemie Odzyskane 1945-2005. Ziemie Zachodnie i Północne. 60 lat w granicach państwa polskiego*, ed. by Andrzej Sakson (Poznań: Instytut Zachodni, 2006), pp. 45–58.

⁶⁸ Sławomir Łotysz, *Pińskie błota: natura, wiedza i polityka na polskim Polesiu do 1945 roku* (Kraków: Universitas, 2023); Kathryn Ciancia, *On Civilization’s Edge: A Polish Borderland in the Interwar World* (Oxford University Press, 2020).

⁶⁹ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

special interest to local officials, including the ‘fifth consecutive governor,’ who, like his predecessors, ‘has something on his conscience in relation to repatriates.’ Perhaps a more vivid depiction can be found in other words from this correspondent, who wrote that ‘the mayors ... when they see a repatriate, get nervous convulsions.’⁷⁰ It shows how the repatriates were depicted as being treated as second-class citizens. The emotions described by the correspondent, manifesting as physical convulsions, were linked to further embodied reactions of the officials towards their clients, characterized by ‘screaming’ and ‘scolding.’ A series of reproaches followed: ‘why did he come here and who dragged him here.’ This not only impeded the resolution of matters in the office but also established a hierarchy among clients: ‘Clerks take an example from their managers and treat them [repatriates] similarly, often postponing the settlement of their affairs to the day after tomorrow without considering the tens of kilometres they [repatriates] have travelled on foot.’ In this hierarchy, repatriates occupied the lowest position, continually lectured, indicating that they were perceived as lacking knowledge. The correspondent saw the resolution in slow normalization of the relations: ‘... it takes time and a strong hand to convert an official, and converting them will have a positive impact on the other resettlers.’⁷¹ In other words, only when officials who set an example for others have been addressed will repatriates cease to be treated as second-class citizens.

The perception of repatriates as lacking sufficient knowledge was most acutely manifested in the process of ‘settling the matter.’ This enigmatic term encompasses virtually any activity that required visiting an office, engaging with an official, and, finally, possessing the requisite knowledge to successfully ‘settle the matter.’ Unlike the concept of ‘combination’—a strategy for navigating the post-war recovered territories described by Edyta Materka⁷²—‘settling the matter’ entailed a different approach. Materka describes combination as bending the rules to achieve goals; however, settling the matter involved understanding and recognizing the established rules. Repatriates were often thrust into a challenging situation: they were unsure with whom to settle the matter, how to proceed, and how to expedite the process. Thus, the rules were not bent but rather acknowledged. In this context, repatriates were at a significant disadvantage, as the rules were established prior to their arrival and were often based on values and customs unfamiliar to them. In this way, geographical proximity advantaged those who arrived earlier from closer areas and disadvantaged repatriates for these same reasons.

By in-depth analysis of the reports of correspondents, it becomes apparent that the process of settling the matter often relied on connections and acquaintances. These connections were frequently linked to geographical proximity and status within the group of settlers. In other words, it was necessary to know not only how, but also with whom, by whom, and with what a given matter could be settled. The relationships among settlers were influenced by the timing of their arrival, their ability to establish connections, and the presence of a larger group of acquaintances from their past, such as those coming from the same region. A correspondent from Wałcz observed that some settlers, clearly not referring to the resettlers, ‘accustomed to a different order of things, sometimes cannot cope with life.’⁷³ A correspondent from the county of Łobez put it more bluntly: ‘What can’t be done [in our land] over a glass [of vodka]?’⁷⁴ This statement clearly indicated the significance of social currency in the post-war reality, with the glass of vodka symbolizing the practice of settling matters through social

⁷⁰ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁷¹ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁷² Edyta Materka, *Dystopia’s Provocateurs: Peasants, State, and Informality in the Polish-German Borderlands* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2017).

⁷³ Anonymous, September 1947, MZO AMR, folio 123.

⁷⁴ Anonymous, February 1948, MZO AMR, folio 232.

connections. This was also a favoured currency during the period in which the analysed documents were created: although the new Polish state resumed the activities of the State Spirit Monopoly as early as November 1944,⁷⁵ the organization of the monopoly was only completed in the autumn of 1948. During this crisis period, marked by severe economic difficulties, alcohol became a means of economic exchange, more stable than other currencies, especially when the real value of the national currency was in doubt. A glass of vodka was not only an effective way to settle matters in general, but also expedited the process. As the correspondent from Pyrzyce noted, ‘in many cases, vodka is the best incentive to get things done right away.’⁷⁶ However, as he added, ‘not everyone can afford such an incentive.’⁷⁷ Thus, the economic stratification of the settlers became apparent, as access to goods, including alcohol, was already constrained by prior access to other resources.

The issue of geographical proximity as an advantage was present in the reports sent by a correspondent from Łobez who provided numerous examples in which resettlers from Central Poland more easily ‘settled’ their matters through acquaintances, or as he termed them, ‘personal-family contacts.’⁷⁸ This allowed them to achieve greater success in offices compared to repatriates. This was also because, as mentioned earlier, the majority of officials were recruited from Central Poland. Therefore, a client seeking a positive resolution to their matter needed to be familiar with local networks of connections, possess the appropriate currency, and—last but not least—have time. The correspondent from Pyrzyce added that ‘there are regulations on issuing ration cards to repatriates, but those who are closer to the centre will get these cards.’⁷⁹ ‘Closer’ in this case could mean having acquaintances, but it could also indicate the speed of queuing: here, the fate of the client seems to be similar to that of an official, as one correspondent complained about the impossibility of queuing for bread during working hours. Again, the close proximity to the office proves to be dual in nature: both in a literal spatial sense and in a more metaphorical one.

Further analysis of the contacts mentioned by the correspondent from Łobez reveals that proximity to the centre could have been influenced by party affiliation. In the struggle for goods between repatriates and resettlers, the repatriates were often at a disadvantage, as exemplified by the observation that the repatriate, ‘this poor fellow, does not belong to any party, etc.’⁸⁰ It was noted by more correspondents: ‘We have enough valuable people in this group [repatriates], but ... [they] avoid parties like the plague, and because of that they are hardly to be found in district, city or commune councils; in the positions of mayors or commune heads, or in some other managerial positions, because these candidates are nominated by parties that lack repatriates.’⁸¹ The fact that someone knew a party member or was a party member themselves played a significant role in settling matters. This was evident on site, as one correspondent suggested that the solution to the low status of repatriates in local hierarchies would be to ‘draw them to offices, and to assign at least some of the leadership positions [to them],’ which ‘would also contribute to a faster elimination of friction [between them and the resettlers from Central Poland].’⁸² At the same time, this statement highlights the issue of the low number of repatriates among the officials.

The reason for the distrust of the repatriates towards the parties was not directly addressed by correspondents. However, it was also connected to why they had to settle in the

⁷⁵ Krzysztof Kosiński, *Historia pijaństwa w czasach PRL: Polityka, obyczaje, szara strefa, patologie* (Warszawa: Neriton, 2008).

⁷⁶ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁷⁷ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁷⁸ Anonymous, February 1948, MZO AMR, folio 232.

⁷⁹ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁸⁰ Anonymous, February 1948, MZO AMR, folio 232.

⁸¹ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

⁸² Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

recovered territories in the first place: their experiences in Soviet Russia and the conclusions drawn from those experiences about the party as such. Additionally, the new authorities they distrusted were the same ones who, by legitimizing the incorporation of the recovered territories, agreed to the loss of the Eastern Borderlands to the Soviet Union. This, in turn, meant losing all hope of the repatriates returning to their small homelands. The frequent mentions of injustices perpetrated by the Communists indicate that it was not a fear of a party in general, but a fear of this specific party. One correspondent noted that ‘one of the unpleasant symptoms of socio-economic life is measuring people by party affiliation. The Polish Workers’ Party ID entitles you to everything. A member may receive a horse, a cow, and all kinds of allowances. Others also receive, but in an insignificant percentage. When any of the party members goes against the law, he hides behind the party and gets away with it. These incidents happen quite often.’⁸³ These fears and conflicts were exacerbated by the evident conflict between the Polish Workers’ Party, the Polish Socialist Party, and the Polish People’s Party, especially during the years when the correspondents wrote their reports.⁸⁴ Membership in the Polish Workers’ Party and the privileges associated with it complicated local relations, particularly since, as we have seen, group of resettlers from Central Poland partially overlapped with the group of people who belonged to the party.

To summarize, the correspondents transmitted a specific geographical imagination of the repatriates. Their reports, submitted to the bureau and subsequently to the Ministry, as evidenced by the archival corpus under scrutiny, reinforced the ambiguous position of the Kresy in Polish discourse post-1945, intertwining it with the concept of “recovery.” In turn, they constituted a distinct worldmaking practice. In their reports, it occurred without explaining why the Borderlands were no longer part of Poland or the direct causes of the forced migration of the repatriates. To this end, the term “repatriation” was utilized, which is the best visible meaning-making tool of this specific geographical imagination: it constructed a narrative that influenced the perceptions of both repatriates and resettlers for further use in discourse on the recovered territories. Coupled with the substantial distance the repatriates had to travel, this shaped not only their experiences upon settling in the recovered territories but also how they were perceived. Repatriates, who had endured significant losses and lengthy journeys, often regarded the recovered territories as temporary settlements. In contrast, resettlers from Central Poland, who faced shorter journeys, swiftly established local networks and leveraged connections to their advantage. They justified their actions by viewing the recovered territories not only as a new home but also as compensation for their sacrifices during the war in German-occupied lands. These disparate experiences resulted in on-site socio-economic hierarchies, as observed by the correspondents. Consequently, these processes highlighted the complex interplay between geographical distance, historical context, and emotional responses in shaping the settlers’ lives in the recovered territories.

Geographical Imagination II: Correspondents as Settlers

As Hannah Arendt pointed out, bureaucracy as a system affects both officials and clients.⁸⁵ Because it firmly separates one from the other, officials often feel that their actions have no consequences in the lives of their clients, which makes them less likely to use their conscience. In the case of bureaucracy in the recovered territories, the situation was not always so clear. The separation of officials from their clients was often blurred because the vast

⁸³ Anonymous, May 1947, MZO AMR, folio 61.

⁸⁴ Katarzyna Rembacka, *Komunista na peryferiach władzy: Historia Leonarda Borkowicza (1912-1989)* (Szczecin-Warszawa: Instytut Pamięci Narodowej, 2020).

⁸⁵ Hannah Arendt, *The Human Condition* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1958).

majority of individuals from both groups came to this region from outside. The newly emerging societies in the recovered territories took shape in an uncertain time, in chaos, and without intermediate structures,⁸⁶ hence the bureaucratic power over clients had to be different.

As we know, the majority of correspondents were recruited from among local officials. This situation is well-reflected in the preserved archival corpus of the correspondents' reports. However, apart from the supposedly 'objective' reports on the situation in the recovered territories, correspondents also constructed their own self-image. This was done explicitly, partially to legitimize their claims in the face of enforced anonymization. Implicit elements of self-creation are also present in the reports, allowing us to better understand the correspondents' positions as settlers themselves, and thus to see how they depicted settlers from within. This constitutes another form of worldmaking and results in another geographical imagination.

The mentions allowing us to identify individual anonymized correspondents in terms of their occupation are incidental. This is exemplified by a correspondent from Gryfino County. In April 1947, he complained that: '... rarely do bakeries bake bread, and then only those who patiently wait from the moment the bread is put into the oven can buy it. Officials who are in the office do not have the opportunity to buy one.'⁸⁷ The specific attention to the plight of officials, who, due to their fixed work hours, cannot stand in line for bread, and the emphasis placed on this situation by the correspondent, suggest that this issue was acutely felt by him. Therefore, it is plausible that the correspondent was a clerk who personally experienced the problem of bread scarcity.

This complaint, however, could be interpreted in a different light. An analysis of various officials' profiles, as documented in the preserved archival materials of individual offices throughout Western and Central Pomerania, reveals that the notion of fixed office hours was frequently foreign to officials working there in the second half of the 1940s. For example, in the preserved personal files of officials from Gryfice, complaints about clerks arriving late or leaving work early, in addition to coming to work in a state of intoxication, are very common.⁸⁸ Thus, the Gryfino county correspondent did not merely lament the challenging circumstances faced by a clerk but also crafted an image of a diligent official who remains committed to their duties even in the face of the threat of a shortage of basic food products.

It is particularly valuable to examine the complaints that correspondents included in their reports to the bureau. This approach reverses the common saying in studies of bureaucracy: that the officials are a group about which 'so much has been written and yet they remained so anonymous.'⁸⁹ While it is true that many studies of bureaucracy address complaints about officials, examining the specific grievances of correspondents can shed additional light on the strategies of worldmaking we are following. The complaints typically concern official competences, privileges associated with being an official, and the circumstances in which one holds office. In the post-war reality of the recovered territories, the office primarily served as a place where goods were distributed. In the context of widespread shortages, this role was crucial not only due to the lack of items but also because of incoming aid in the form of, for example, animals or material goods, which were then distributed to those in need. In the formerly German territories, it also involved the allocation of what had been left by the Germans.

⁸⁶ Stanisław Łach, *Przemiany społeczno-polityczne na Pomorzu Zachodnim, 1945-1950* (Poznań: Wydawnictwo Poznańskie, 1978).

⁸⁷ Anonymous, April 1947, MZO AMR, folio 32.

⁸⁸ Reports in the folder Zarząd Miejski i Miejska Rada Narodowa w Gryficach, State Archive in Szczecin, branch of Międzyzdroje.

⁸⁹ John Brewer, *The Sinews of Power: War, Money, and the English State, 1688-1783* (Harvard University Press, 1990).

Thus, the examination of complaints submitted by correspondents reveals significant insights into the post-war allocation of resources in the recovered territories. For instance, the correspondent from Białogard reported that ‘... there are individuals who are not farmers, but work, for example, in the commune’s office, [and] they have cows allocated, and farmers [who have] farms of several hectares do not have them.’⁹⁰ Here, officials are depicted as individuals who, despite not needing a cow due to the absence of a large farm, possessed this particularly valuable commodity. The importance of cows during this period was underscored by the fact that the Scientific Council of the Bureau issued a separate opinion on their allocation.

Overall, the correspondents’ reports highlight widespread issues related to the competence and discipline of office personnel in the post-war recovered territories. The most frequent complaint was that the office personnel were incompetent and undisciplined. The correspondent from Pyrzyce categorized them into looters, bribe-takers, and careerists. The correspondent from Piła went even further, highlighting their general ‘lack of sense of duty’ at every level. He primarily attributed this to circumstances such as ‘lack of routine,’ which can be interpreted as the instability of the situation, the constant changes in regulations, and the turnover of personnel responsible for enforcing them, as well as the lack of ‘professional education’ or ‘knowledge of one’s own field.’⁹¹ In general, the correspondent from Koszalin lamented the lack of ‘qualified officials,’ attributing this to low salaries. He pointed out the salary of the commune secretary, hinting at a possible personal connection to this role. On the other hand, some municipalities in Western and Central Pomerania experienced prolonged vacancies in this position, suggesting that the secretary’s salary was almost proverbially low remuneration for demanding work. In turn, an unattractive salary combined with high expectations resulted in understaffed offices, with employees consequently overloaded with duties. According to the correspondent from Piła, this situation led to employees performing their work unwittingly, which then resulted in ‘chaos and mess’⁹² in the offices. Consequently, both the office and the clients remained dissatisfied.

Examining the reports of individual correspondents reveals the worldmaking practices they pursued as anonymous reporters for the bureau. For instance, the correspondent from Pyrzyce, whose report was the longest among the preserved excerpts sent by the bureau to the Ministry, demonstrated extensive knowledge about the activities of the Repatriation Office and settlement reports in counties. He described conflicts over property and objects left by Germans, explaining that he gathered information by driving around the district and observing both ‘men in the streets’ and ‘big fish in offices,’⁹³ recounting how he intervened in some cases, putting himself in difficult situations. Thus, he may have worked in the Repatriation Office, or he could have been, for example, an agricultural instructor who, while touring the county, had contact with both farmers and the administrative authorities. Notably, the characteristics based on the descriptions of the correspondents and their worldmaking practices suggest that they could have been both officials and interested parties, subjects of extremely burdensome bureaucratic practices. The correspondent from Pyrzyce could be imagined as both an inquisitive official and an educated settler who represented the problems of his group in their interactions with the nascent Polish bureaucracy.

Ultimately, the context of attempts to outline the image of local relations and the self-creation of the creators of the sources, the correspondents of the bureau, within the anonymous reality of excerpts from studies reveals the worldmaking practices occurring on-site in the dynamic process of creating new local societies in the recovered territories, which

⁹⁰ Anonymous, May 1947, MZO AMR, folio 57.

⁹¹ Anonymous, March 1947, MZO AMR, folio 115.

⁹² Anonymous, March 1947, MZO AMR, folio 115.

⁹³ Anonymous, February 1947, MZO AMR, folio 128.

resulted in particular geographical imaginations. The correspondents, despite their anonymization, do not merely accept the new socio-political reality but actively design it on-site and craft alternative geographical imaginations where the foremost place is occupied by the efforts and oversights of the clerks.

Conclusions

The preserved archival corpus allowed me to analyze the worldmaking practices that resulted in geographical imaginations of the postwar reality in formerly German regions incorporated by Poland in 1945. These worldmaking practices were evident in two intertwined cases: the scientifically-led organization of resettlement, overseen by the Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies and its Scientific Council, and the anonymous correspondents. The former were officially renowned and served as scholarly authorities, while the latter remained nameless and were reduced to a handful of geographical information. As I have demonstrated, this anonymity did not hinder the correspondents' attempts to influence the situation and, in turn, create distinctive geographical imaginations concerning the displaced Poles from the Kresy, as well as the correspondents themselves as both officials and settlers. Moreover, this analysis revealed the underlying inequalities within the organization of the scientific bodies responsible for resettlement, as they were also treated with a degree of distance by the Ministry, which was tasked with organizing the settlement until 1949.

What is more, the preserved archival corpus allowed me to trace these worldmaking practices based on the materials provided and archived by the subjects who created them. It equips us with the vocabulary that the actors of the time used or tried to use. The bureaucratic process of 'settling the matter' becomes here a dynamic form of creating various social forms: it changes the purpose of places and determines property rights, determines what is legal and what is not, often by unwritten rules; it indicates belonging to a specific group, not only ethnic or national, but also in internal local discourses of the recovered territories, to a given group of settlers.

Thus, the analyzed material shows that the geographical imaginations under scrutiny were influenced by ideas about the recovered territories and the new Poland in general. This is evident not only in the concerns surrounding the officials engaged in the settlement process. Instead of a competent individual capable of discerning the needs of a given group emotionally—an official situated somewhere within the Weberian ideal type of bureaucrat but equipped with emotional discernment resulting from wartime experiences and associated social traumas—there were complaints about officials being guided by self-interest. These clerks interacted with settlers, who were also not free from the vision of the ideal: they were expected to be devoted to their work, arriving in the recovered territories voluntarily to build a new world, and guided not by personal interests but by the interests of the state.

In addition, the tension related to the increasing power of the communists is evident. The declared democracy, which asserted that one did not need specific competences to become an official and supported the image of thoroughly 'people's' power, clashed with the demand for professionalism and competence, features frequently mentioned by the correspondents. This new world could be understood simultaneously as a world of socialism under construction, in which class divisions would be obliterated, and as a world of a homogeneous Polish community that could be built from scratch in regions with a somewhat 'nullified' history, where the entire period separating the medieval state of the Piasts from the spring of 1945 had disappeared.

These ideals clashed directly with the concrete realities of individuals and their problems. Information on the conduct of both officials and their clients in the postwar recovered territories—characterized by a complicated ownership structure, chaos of orders, and attempts to build new lives—reveals that contact with bureaucracy soon transformed

settlers into either officials or clients. This information can be drawn from extensive excerpts contained in the reports sent to the bureau by its correspondents. In the broader context of scientific resettlement, this documentation functioned as a tool of knowledge production, with a relatively small influence on the means of governance. However, the bureau's role was not merely descriptive but prescriptive—by collecting and categorizing field reports, it framed various groups of settlers, stressing what required intervention in the process of resettlement. Ultimately, the circulation and use of the documents collected by the bureau from its correspondents demonstrate how archives were not necessarily only passive repositories but active instruments in worldmaking.

Furthermore, such an analysis of the documents left by the bureau allowed me to investigate the role of offices and their staff in shaping social and political life in Poland in the first decades after the war, particularly how subjects and social life were constructed in the new post-war reality of the formerly German lands. In the two case studies under scrutiny, I analyzed how the bureau and its correspondents produced and archived various types of documents that reveal their worldmaking practices in these areas. I argue that these documents show how they designed a new socio-political reality and fashioned geographical imaginations, with the constant tension between the lost East, the 'recovered' West, and the ambiguous role of Central Poland or 'Elder Lands.' Thus, I demonstrated the worldmaking practices found in the preserved archival documents. Furthermore, I addressed not only how the bureaucracy in these areas created internal hierarchies and power relations, but also how the tension between legitimization by known authorities and on-site data gathered from anonymous correspondents influenced the imagined geographies of the Polish postwar period, which continue to have ongoing ramifications.

For both the correspondents and the bureau, documentation served distinct but interconnected purposes. For correspondents—settlers themselves—reporting allowed them to actively participate in shaping the discourse on resettlement, attempting to acknowledge their lived realities within the bureaucratic framework. However, their anonymization also meant that their agency was subsumed within the broader scientific narrative. For the bureau, documentation was a means of exerting control over the resettlement process, translating fragmented, on-the-ground realities into quantifiable, analyzable data. By standardizing and archiving these reports, the bureau wanted to transform resettlement from a chaotic and often spontaneous movement into a scientific and systematic process. However, a meta-commentary to the analysis presented here is a pencil note found on a letter sent from the bureau to the Ministry of the Recovered Territories in the summer of 1947. This note suggests that, despite continued efforts, central-level officials were aware that the planned settlement action no longer had any sense or possibility of materializing. The inscription reads: 'the remarks rather too late.'⁹⁴

Acknowledgments

The article is funded by the National Science Centre in Poland under the project "Documents and Bureaucracy in the Formerly German Lands: State Making, Regulating and Controlling in Poland and Czechoslovakia (1940s-1970s)", no. 2021/41/B/HS3/00118

⁹⁴ Biuro Studiów Osadniczo-Przesiedleńczych [the Bureau of Settlement and Resettlement Studies] to Departament Osiedleńczy [Department of Resettlement] at the Ministry of the Recovered Territories, 14 July 1947, MZO AMR, folio 1.